

Relationship between Health and Hygiene based on Bangladesh Labor Law 2006 and Perceived Workplace Environmental Satisfaction: A Study on Jute Industry in Khulna, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between health and hygiene practices based on Bangladesh labor law 2006 and worker's perceived workplace environment satisfaction in jute industry in Khulna. Health and hygiene practices in Bangladesh labor law 2006 includes regarding cleanliness, ventilation and temperature, drinking water, litigating and latrines and washrooms. This research find outs the relative predictive power of each items to the change of worker's perceive workplace environmental satisfaction. Cleanliness has largest impact on the change of worker's perceive workplace environmental satisfaction and more than 50% of change in the worker's perceived workplace satisfaction can be explained by cleanliness. Ventilation and temperature, drinking water, and lighting has respectively 31%,28% and 13% predictive power to impact and can explain the change of worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction. The target population of this study consists of all the employees who are working in the Jute industry in Bangladesh. The data was collected from 102 workers and employees of private and public jute mill in Khulna. The research was quantitative in nature. Here in this research nonprobability convenience sampling method was used. A five-point liker scale is used for designing the questionnaire and data was analyzed through SPSS software. This research will help will help Hr. professionals working in the jute industry, management of the organization in jute mills, ministry of textiles and jute and overall the government of Bangladesh can get a better the understanding of current scenario health and hygiene practices are maintained in jute industry and its impacts on worker's workplace environmental satisfaction.

Keywords: Workplace, Satisfaction, Health, Hygiene, Environmental.

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Last decades workplace environment has obtained significant attention to the companies because employees spend their most valuable and productive time to the workplace and workplace environmental satisfaction ensures organization's efficiency and effectiveness. Workplace satisfied employee becomes happier and self-confident and can do amazing things which is so important for organization's competitiveness and for survival in the market (power 2016). Maintaining health and hygiene to the workplace has become major concern to the human resource professionals and they are responsible for this. Health and hygiene has immense importance to ensure a healthy and safe workplace (employsure 2019). Bangladesh is the second largest jute producing country in the world and Bangladesh produce finest quality jute fiber in the world. Jute is now one of the most popular natural fibers worldwide due to its biodegradability and composability. So, the potential of jute and jute products is growing day by day as an eco-friendly natural commodity. Hessian cloth, jute carpets, bags, ropes, and twines are traditionally made from jute produced in this region. Bangladeshi manufacturers and exporters are now concentrating on diversified jute products due to growing global demand. The government ban on the manufacture, selling and use of polythene in 2002 and made it mandatory for packing rice, sugar, wheat and fertilizers in jute bags in 2010, also encouraged producers to expand the jute-goods market (Jute Industry in Bangladesh | History, Problems, and Prospects, 2021). The contribution of the jute industry to Bangladesh's economy is massive. Over the years, this sector has directly and indirectly provided jobs for a large segment of the country's total population. Per year, Bangladesh produces 8.5-9.0 million (85-900 lakh) raw jute bales, of which approximately 7.5 million (75 lakh) bales are used in the country jute mills. The country exports 0.8 million (8 lakh) jute bales. Export income from these bales is 854 corer taka. Bangladesh produces approximately 5 lakh tones jute goods of which country exports approximately 4 lakh tones and export income is 3051 corer Taka (Ministry of jute and textile 2021). Khulna is the most significant zone for jute industry in Bangladesh cause there are nine state run jute mills and around 50 private jute mills are available in Khulna which corresponds 71 percent of total jute mills of Bangladesh. There are almost 30000 workers are employed at the nine state run jute mills. (MEMBERS LIST – Bangladesh Jute Spinners Association, 2021). Human resource management is a fundamental function of an organization to keep the organization running or to keep organization's operation successful. Most of the jute mills practice basic hr. functions like manpower planning and handling entire recruitment procedure, job advertisement, review, screening of application and finalizing the process of appointment, managing orientation

program, performance appraisal, ensuring training and development program to retain staff and increase skill and knowledge. HR manager has responsibility to direct and control overall HR, Administration, and compliance with law such as labor law(Manager (HR & Admin) at Altu Khan Jute Mills Ltd (A Sister Concern of Panna Group) | Dohaj.com, 2021).

Objectives of the study

Main Objective: The main purpose of this objective is to conduct a comprehensive study to find out the relationship between health and hygiene practices based on Bangladesh labor law 2006 and perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

The Specific Objectives

Followings are the specific objectives of the present study:

- i. To find out present scenario regarding health and hygiene practices in jute mills in Bangladesh.
- ii. To find out the degree of workplace environmental satisficing in jute industry in Bangladesh.
- iii. To identify how much and how many jute mills follow the health and hygiene practices included in Bangladesh labor law 2006.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human resource professionals are responsible for managing all employee related functions of an organization. Maintaining health and hygiene in the workplace is one of the major concerns of hr. professionals now days. In the workplace, hygiene is crucial because it contributes to a safe workforce. A healthier workforce is happier and productive. A healthy workplace often ensures that less sick leave is taken by workers. This would minimize the tremendous cost to businesses (Employure 2019).Implementing hygiene practices is a major challenge in developing countries like Bangladesh (kumwenda 2019). Hygiene has been identified to minimize, among many other things including diarrheal diseases and illnesses, and good hygiene practices improve dignity, self-esteem and prestige in social life (kumwenda 2019).

Health and Hygiene factors: It has become so necessary to take care of one's health and hygiene in modern times. With growing population levels, levels of pollution, emissions of toxic gases, ensuring their health and hygiene must be a priority for all. To ensure health and hygiene of workers Bangladesh labor code 2006 have a separate chapter which includes separate subsections regarding cleanliness, dust

and fume, ventilation and temperature, disposal of waste, lighting, drinking water, overcrowding, latrines and washrooms, dust bins and spittoons. This paper focus on the separate subsections regarding health and hygiene practices in this chapter.

Cleanliness: In a clean office environment, workers are the most efficient and have the best job efficiency (Salone, 2012). An unclean and untidy workplace atmosphere contributes to employee dissatisfaction and tension (Salone, 2012). Bangladesh labor code 2006 say that every establishment shall be kept clean and free from effluvia arising from any drain, privy or other nuisance. (Horrevorts, Ophem and Terpstra, 2018) conducted a research on 2018 and the paper showed that there is a strong positive correlation between cleanness and the productivity of employees. Bangladesh labor code says that in every establishment where dust and fume or other impurity of such nature and to such extent as is likely to be injurious or offensive to workers employed therein, effective measures shall be taken to prevent it's accumulation in any workroom and it's inhalation by workers. Author L. Jayne Baudin saw dust and fumes as a significant danger of modern industry and she wrote more than 100 years ago "dust and smoke have a great influence upon the mortality of a locality, especially in deaths from lung diseases." She recommended that workdays be shortened to 10 hours for men and eight hours for youths, and that "pauses in the work" be taken to allow workers time away from the dust.

the principle danger of modern industry are dust and fume (Baudin)(n,d).The effect of street dust is noticeable cause some years ago in new York city, one third of the workers employed for cleaning street was affected by tuberculosis. They were examined before employment. (Baudin, 2018). Bangladesh labor code, 2006 provides obligation that effective arrangements shall be made in every establishment for the disposal of wastes and effluents due to the manufacturing process carried on therein. Waste management continues to be a major challenge in urban areas worldwide, especially in the fast-growing cities of the developing world (Barnabas, Sivakumar, pandian and Geetha, 2019). A high population growth rate and growing per capita income have contributed to the development of enormous solid waste, which poses a significant threat to the quality of the environment and to human health (Abed in and Jahiruddin, 2015). Bangladesh labor code 2006 says that in every establishment there shall be provided a sufficient number of dust beans which shall be maintained in a clean and hygienic condition and this law also obligates that no person shall spit within the premises of the establishment as well as a notice containing this provision and the penalty for this violation shall be prominently displayed at suitable places in the premises.

Ventilation and Temperature: Bangladesh labor code 2006 says that effective measures should be undertaken in every establishment for securing and maintaining in every workroom adequate ventilation by the circulation of fresh air. It also obligates that temperature in every room shall be kept in a reasonable condition that provides comfort to the workers. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) reports that people spend about 90% of their time indoors in the Western world (Indoor Air Quality | US EPA, n.d.). Furthermore, studies show that indoor air in different commercial institutions is five times more polluted than outdoor air (Indoor Air Quality | US EPA, n.d.). Air particles come in a number of ways, ranging from animal dander, plant spores, bacteria, fiberglass and asbestos to particles of combustion (Indoor Air Quality | US EPA, n.d.). Up to 500,000 particles (0.3 mm) per minute are dispersed by people without movement (Indoor Air Quality | US EPA, n.d.). This amount can reach up to 45,000,000 particles (0.3 mm) per minute when active (Fluke Corporation, 2005). Bangladesh labor code, 2006 says that no workroom in any establishment shall be overcrowded to an extent injurious to the health of the workers employed therein. And also mention that 9.5 cubic meter of space for every worker shall be provided. In general, crowding refers to the psychological reaction of people to density, i.e. their feelings of being crowded, loss of privacy or a rise in unwelcome interactions or psychological distress (Gray, 2001). Myers et al. (1996) dealt with overcrowded housing as an important factor affecting housing policy since it is hazardous to people's physical and mental health. Overcrowded housing, for example, can lead to high infant mortality (Cage and Foster, 2002).

Lightning: Bangladesh labor code says regarding lightning that in every part of establishment where workers are working or passing, there shall be provided or maintained sufficient and suitable lightning, natural or artificial, or both. This sections also obligates that all glazed windows and skylights used for lightning of the workroom shall be kept clean on both outer and inner surfaces and free from obstruction as far as possible. Kataro & yan (2019) conducted a research on the effects of lightning quality on efficiency of workers in office building in Tanzania and reported that poor indoor environmental quality such as lighting has a detrimental effect on human health, and in case of the office working population, it affects their work performance as well. Many studies consider both qualitative and quantitative dimensions of workplace illumination as the main factors assessing the efficiency of the employees. The ambient lighting conditions all affect the tempo, excellence, interruptions, truancy and injury rate of the employees (G. Hoffmann, V. Gufler, A. Griesmacher et al, 2008).

Drinking Water: Bangladesh labor code 2006 says that in every establishment effective arrangement shall be made to provide and maintain at a suitable point conveniently suited for all workers employed therein, a sufficient supply of wholesome pure drinking water.

Human body has 70% water so water is very essential for each part of a human body. Pure drinking water removes toxins, improves our complexion, relieves headaches, promotes weight loss, and aids in digestion. When poor quality of water is taken, people feel sluggish, bloated, and dehydrated without proper amount of high quality of water (Why Safe, Pure Water is Important to Your Health | Charger Water Treatment Products, n.d.).

The use of the purest source of water has become a must for a safe life. The definition of basic water requirements is introduced by Peter Gleick, president of the Pacific Institute for Studies in Development, analyzes the quantities of water needed for different basic needs. He concludes that a daily range of 20 to 40 liters of freshwater per capita is commonly considered to be the minimum needed to fulfill drinking and sanitation requirements alone. If water for bathing and cooking is also included, this number ranges from 27 to 200 liters per person per day. It is estimated that around 37.7 million Indians are affected by water borne diseases annually, 1.5 million children are estimated to die of diarrhea alone and 73 million working days are lost due to waterborne disease each year. The resulting economic burden is estimated at \$600 million a year. (Khurana and Sen, 2007).

Latrines and Washrooms: Bangladesh labor code, 2006 says that in every establishment sufficient latrines and washrooms shall be provided such latrines and washrooms shall be provided separately for male and female workers. This law also obligates that latrines and washrooms should adequately lighted, ventilated and supplied with water all time as well as maintained in a clean and sanitary condition at all times with suitable detergents and disinfectants. Just Humphrey (2009) hypothesized that the predominant causal pathway from poor sanitation and hygiene to under nutrition is tropical/environmental enteropathy, not diarrhea.

Perceived Workplace Environmental Satisfaction: Workplace can be defined as the place where employees of a certain organizations work together for a defined period of time regularly within an infrastructural and environmental setup (workplace, 2020).

The work environment consists of a workplace's physical, geographical location and immediate surroundings (including factors such as air quality, noise level, etc.), as well as employment-related advantages and benefits. Staff members who are pleased with their work environment would most likely comply with the rules and interests of the company. They tend to place their personal interests behind

the company and refrain from unethical actions such as bribery, embezzlement, taking bribes, participating in corrupt practices, or stealing as they seek to retain their position. The employees don't want to move another company unless he/she doesn't get better or same environment he/she work in and they want same environment to others organizations. (Satisfactory work environment and conditions - WIN - Water Integrity Network, 2019),

Workplace environment has become one of the major concerned areas of human resource management professional during the past decades. Modern human resource management considers workplace environment as an important issue as employees spend the most productive times of their life in the workplace (power 2016). This is why human resource management tries to increase employee's positive thinking about the workplace environment which can be termed as workplace environmental satisfaction. Wai and Brubaker, (2014) explored that workplace environmental satisfaction or work environment is highly responsible for increasing the overall job satisfaction and employees intention to stay in the organization. Good workplace environment ensures organization's efficiency, effectiveness, productivity and job commitment of employees and good workplace environment has great impact on job satisfaction (Raziq and Maulabakhsh, 2015) Workplace environmental satisfied workers remains happy and becomes loyal to their companies and loyal employees can do amazing things which is important for company's success that's why many leading company like Google, Apple, software analytics giant institute SAS have paid great attention to the betterment of workplace environment (power 2016) Workplace environmental satisfaction works as some sort of medicine because it reduces stress of an employee and this reduction of stress occurs instant productivity boost of an organization (power 2016). Workplace environmental satisfied employees are more willing to support fellow workers and provide positive support and encouragement for project work as well as satisfied workers ask more help than dissatisfied workers to the group members (power 2016). Employees of a good workplace environment becomes supportive to each other and encourages their team member to learn from mistakes rather than fearing the mistakes that's why workplace environmental satisfied workers are not afraid to make mistake (power 2016). Employees of a good workplace environment becomes supportive to each other and encourages their team member to learn from mistakes rather than fearing the mistakes that's why workplace environmental satisfied workers are not afraid to make mistake (power 2016). A workplace environmental satisfied worker really enjoys his work that makes him attentive and productive at his work. Above all this increases self-confidence and inspires better performance and greater success (power 2016). Perceived workplace environmental satisfaction is employees' perception about the degree to which the workplace environment ensure employee retention and this reduce employee recruitment and retention cost .A workplace

environmental satisfied employee feels proud of working there. (Fusculdo, 2020). A good workplace environment helps to boost employee morale, retention and productivity (Freedman, 2020). At a good workplace environment employee should have time to have fun with their friends and colleagues Besides some company encourage their employee to exercise cause this improve their health, mood and freshness as well as their productivity (Brown, n.d.).

Most of the organization which has good workplace environment facilitates social interaction with their family and friends as well as colleague these organization allows family and friends of employees to visit the workplace or organization (Chen, Hall, Yu and Qian, 2019). Many organizations design their workplace environment in such a way so that the employee does not feel suffocated. Some organization adopt green environment in the workplace by planting trees in the workplace (Dutta, 2020) orkplace environment is capable of meeting employees' expectation (Lee, 2016).

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Figure: This figure shows the relationship between health and hygiene practices and workplace environmental satisfaction

The purpose of the study is to observe the relationship between health and hygiene practices based on labor law 2006 and workplace environmental satisfaction in jute industry in Khulna, Bangladesh. There are five dimensions in health and hygiene factors and workers workplace environmental satisfaction depends on it. So here health and hygiene factor is independent variable and workers environmental satisfaction is dependent variable.

HYPOTHESIS

H1: Cleanliness has positive relationship with perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

H2: Ventilation and Temperature has positive relationship with workplace environmental satisfaction.

H3: Lighting has positive relationship with perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

H4: Drinking water has positive relationship with perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

H5: Latrines and washrooms have positive relationship with perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

H6: Health and hygiene practices based on Bangladesh labor law 2006 has a positive relationship with perceived workplace environmental satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

The chapter focuses on the description of the research design, the population of the study, sampling procedure, data collection method, questionnaire design, and data analysis method

Research Design

The research uses the analysis methods considering the essence and all research criteria. The research is essentially carried out to test the hypothesis about health and hygiene practices based on Bangladesh labor law 2006 and workplace environmental satisfaction in jute industry of Bangladesh. As quantitative research studies are more reliable and easier to quantify and offer more real, reliable and precise results compared to qualitative research studies, this study is quantitative in nature.

The Population Size

All the employee/ workers working in the jute industry in Bangladesh are included in population and according to (STATISTICAL INFORMATION – Bangladesh Jute Spinners Association, 2019) the total population of jute workers are 162000.

BJSA Mills 75,000 BJMA Mills 60,000 BJMC Mills 27,000 **Total: 1, 62,000**

Acronyms Used **BJSA** Bangladesh Jute Spinners Association (Private Sector) **BJMA** Bangladesh Jute Mills Association (Private Sector) **BJMC** Bangladesh Jute Mills Corporation (Public Sector)

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure:

According to Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson and Tatham (1998), at least one hundred sample should be taken for any quantities research in order to fit the statistical method of data analysis.

So, a sample size of total 102 workers working in jute industry in Khulna city were considered for this study.

A survey was performed for the investigation of the research using a nonprobability sampling technique. More precisely, for this particular analysis, a convenience sampling technique was used, which is a specific form of non-probability sampling method focused on collecting data from people who are most conveniently accessible (Zikmund et al., 2016).

For this study, jute mill workers from both private and government owned jute mills in Khulna, Bangladesh, were used as the primary source of data. The study was performed based on the assortment of primary data as the data was collected by the investigator himself for this specific study purpose (Zikmund et al., 2016). There are nine state run jute mills and fifty private owned jute mills and primary data was collected from these places.

RESULT DISCUSSION

The main objective of the study was to find out the relationship between health and hygiene practices based on Bangladesh labor law 2006 and worker's perceived workplace satisfaction in jute industry in Bangladesh. The other objectives was to find out the present scenario of health and hygiene practices and the degree of perceived workplace environmental satisfaction exist in jute industry.

From the analysis of the study, it is revealed that the mean value of latrines and washrooms and lighting are higher than the rest and the values are respectively 3.8 and 3.61, indicating the presence of moderately high level of arrangement at latrines and washrooms and lighting in jute industry, according to the respondents. Additionally, the mean value of health and hygiene practices is 3.27, indicating the presence of moderate level of health and hygiene practices are followed or maintained in jute industry, according to the respondents. On the other hand the mean value of perceived workplace environmental satisfaction is 3.2927, which indicates a moderate level of perceived workplace environmental satisfaction exists in the jute industry in Bangladesh, according to the respondents. In case of company wise, the mean value of health and hygiene practices and worker's perceived workplace environmental

satisfaction of AKIJ, AFIL, ALEEM, AMENA, and KHALISPURE JUTE MILLS are higher than the rest of the companies. The mean value of health and hygiene practices in Akij AKIJ, AFIL, ALEEM, AMENA, and KHALISPURE JUTE MILLS are respectively 3.8, 3.7, 3.9, 3.5, 3.5 which indicate a moderate high level of health and hygiene practices are followed and in consequence the perceived workplace environmental satisfaction is also high in these companies. The mean value of perceived workplace environmental satisfaction are respectively 4.2, 4, 3.9, 3.8, and 3.9.

The rest of the companies have very low level of health and hygiene practices and their low level of worker's workplace environmental satisfaction exist in these companies.

The total mean value of health and hygiene practices and worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction are respectively 3.2729 and 3.2927 which indicate a moderate level of health and hygiene practices are maintained and a moderate level of perceived workplace environmental satisfaction exist in the jute industry in Bangladesh.

The correlation suggests that there is a strong positive relationship between health and hygiene practices and worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction as the Pearson value is .925.

From the regression Analysis we found that, Cleanliness has highest impact to the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction and more than 50% of variance of dependent variable (workplace environmental satisfaction) can be explained by the independent variable (cleanliness). Ventilation and temperature has second largest impact to the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction and 31% of change in workplace environmental satisfaction can be explained by ventilation and temperature. Drinking water has 28% impact on worker's perceived environmental satisfaction. Here 28% change in the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction can be explained by the drinking water (independent variable). Lighting has little contribution to the change of the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction. Only 13% change in the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction can be explained by the lighting (independent variable). , Latrines and washrooms the lowest impact relative to others variables to the worker's perceived workplace environmental satisfaction. Only 3% of change in the worker's perceived workplace environmental can be explained by the latrines and washrooms (independent variable).

The regression analysis validates all of the hypothesis except one (latrines and washrooms).

CONCLUSION

Human resource is the most valuable asset in an organization. Human resource management is the most basic function in any type of organization and not confined in single industry. Jute industry is one of the most significant sector in our country. A large number of workers are employed in this sector. Health and hygiene practices has great impact to the worker's workplace environmental satisfaction. This research will help Hr. professionals working in the jute industry, management of the organization in jute mills, ministry of textiles and jute and overall the government of Bangladesh can get a better the understanding of current scenario health and hygiene practices are maintained in jute industry and its impacts on worker's workplace environmental satisfaction. The government authority those are responsible for implication for laws in jute industry can easily understand how much and how much of law regarding health and hygiene practices included in Bangladesh labor law are being maintained and they can make proper policy for implication of this law. As workplace environmental satisfaction is a significant part of job satisfaction and productivity largely depend on job satisfaction, so the management who wants to increase the production can implement health and hygiene practices in the workplace.

Future Research Direction: Now a day, Workplace health and hygiene issue has become a great concern to the HR professionals and management of organizations as they wants to keep the employee's and worker's both physically and mentally fit. The future researchers can extend the same research nationwide with large sample size in private and government jute mills. Additionally researchers can study on the impacts of health and hygiene practices on worker's personal habits and their family. In the future, the findings of this study can further pave the way for compliance managers in designing and developing policies and procedures for promoting health and hygiene practices in jute industry. Bangladesh labor association (BLA) will get a proper view if which company are following labor law regarding health and hygiene and how much are being maintained. BLA will be able to take proper action for Implication of the law regarding health and hygiene practices.

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